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THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONTEMPORARY CHOREOGRAPHY IN KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract: *This article explores the formation and development of contemporary choreography in the Republic of Kazakhstan. This direction in choreography has experienced the most intensive growth since the Republic of Kazakhstan gained independence. This is due to the fact that, along with the acquisition of independence, both at the state level and in the sphere of art, opportunities arose for freedom of expression in creating and developing new artistic movements.*

Keywords: *Modern, ballet classics, contrast, choreography*

In 1974, Zhanat Baidaralin, a talented graduate of the ballet department at State Institute of Theatre Art, returned to Almaty, marking the beginning of the development of modern dance in Kazakhstan. He staged his graduation production, "Renaissance," to the music of the French composer François Poulenc at the Opera and Ballet Theatre. The ballet is based on Shakespeare's play "Romeo and Juliet," in which Zhanat Baidaralin reveals the love story through the expressive movements of modern dance and classical steps.

The role of Juliet in the ballet was performed by Zarema Kasteyeva, a graduate of the Moscow Choreographic School and a prominent figure in Kazakh ballet of the 1970s and 1980s, People's Artist of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

In 1978, Baidaralin staged the ballet *Aliya*, dedicated to the Great Patriotic War. The ballet is built on contrasts: a tender and fragile girl who becomes a heroic soldier during the terrible years of the war.

In 1980, Zhanat Baidaralin represented the Kazakh SSR in the creation of the opening ceremony of the Moscow Olympic Games with the production *Balbraun*, set to the music of Kurmangazy.

In 1987, Baidaralin staged the modern rock ballet *The Twentieth Century*, set to the music of Jean-Michel Jarre. The performance was staged twice at the Abay State Academic Opera and Ballet Theatre, attracting a surge of audience attention.

Zhanat Baidaralin was both the choreographer and a performer in one of the leading roles in the film *My Brother Mowgli*.

In 1991, he was the first in the CIS to create a private troupe, *Kipchak Dance*, which lasted for about a year.

In 1996, Baidaralin was invited as the principal choreographer for a three-hour theatrical performance dedicated to the anniversary of the Kyrgyz epic poem *Manas*.

For 20 years, Zhanat Baidaralin brought modern dance ideas to life in Kazakhstan, but the contemporary dance scene was not yet mature enough for his work to be widely and officially accepted. In 2000, Zhanat Baidaralin won a U.S. government grant for the American Dance Festival, and in 2001, he emigrated to the United States.

The establishment of the Samruk Contemporary Dance Theater played a significant role in the development and popularization of contemporary dance in Kazakhstan. Since the company's founding, Gulnara Adamova, an Honored Worker of the Republic of Kazakhstan, has served as its artistic director and choreographer.

In 1990, Adamova graduated from the ballet department of the A.V. Lunacharsky Russian Institute of Theatre Arts (Moscow). After graduating, she taught contemporary dance at the Seleznev Academy of Arts, then taught contemporary choreography and ballet directing at the T. Zhurgenov Academy of Arts. She also studied various modern techniques abroad (Austria, Poland, and the Baltic

countries) and attended the renowned Web Festival. During this time, she staged numerous productions and concert numbers for the choreographic school and opera house and choreographed operas and plays.

The Samruk company was founded in 1998, with its first members being former female gymnasts. The troupe first made its mark at the first International Contemporary Dance Festival *Dance Hive*. Since 2003, the Samruk Theatre has received state status and operates under the patronage of the city administration. The Gulnara Adamova Contemporary Ballet Company is a unique professional contemporary dance company in Kazakhstan, working in a wide range of choreographic styles, from neoclassical to contemporary.

The company's repertoire includes full-length productions, one-act ballets, and various forms of choreographic miniatures.

Since the company's founding, its repertoire has significantly expanded and evolved: while works based on various techniques—then new to Kazakhstan—predominated initially, choreographer G. Adamova has recently focused on the possibilities of incorporating national traditions, music, and culture into contemporary choreography.

G. Adamova's productions are regularly performed at the State Academic Opera and Ballet Theatre (GATOB), and the dance theater's repertoire includes *Second Hand*, *Jazz Cafe*, *Farewell on the Milky Way*, *Spiders*, and *Zhestyrnak*.

Sisters Gulmira and Gulnara Gabbasova have had a significant impact on the development of contemporary dance in Kazakhstan. In 1986, the sisters graduated from the Almaty Choreographic School with the qualification of dance ensemble artists. In 1999, they received diplomas from the Zhurgenov State National Academy of Arts as directors and choreographers. In 2004, they completed training at the Palucca Schule (Dresden), where they attended master classes with choreographers from France, England, Portugal, Slovenia, and Russia.

The renowned dancers taught for many years at the Zhurgenov Academy of Arts and the Seleznev Choreographic School, and pursued their dream of founding their own school. The Gabbasov Sisters Company has existed since 2007, and in 2009 the theater acquired a permanent venue. In addition to the professional troupe, there is an amateur troupe composed of the studio's students. The Gulnara and Gulmira Gabbasov Dance Theater combines a studio for those aspiring to dance with a venue for regular performances and creative experimentation. Their productions are known to contemporary dance enthusiasts not only in our country but also far beyond its borders.

The Gabbasov sisters' productions include *Neighbors*, *Miracollo*, *Tamyr*, *Time*, *Without Words*, *The Illusion of Love, or...*, *Female Dogs*, and many others. Since 1999, Kazakhstani audiences have annually seen new performances from the Adamova G. Contemporary Dance Theater and the Gabbasov Sisters' Dance Theater.

One of P. Noel's best students, Asel Abakayeva, remained to teach at the school. In 2002, she completed an internship at the Rik Odoms Institute for Advanced Studies in Paris, danced with the Samruk company, and today teaches modern dance at the T. Zhurgenov Kazakh National Academy of Arts and performs with the professional troupe, the Gabbasov Sisters Company.

In 2004, during the development of the educational standard for the specialty “050409 – Choreography” at the Kazakh State Women's Pedagogical Institute (KazGozhenPI), a program for the *Modern* discipline was developed by Nadezhda Alekseyevna Loskutova, a choreography department instructor and a graduate of Abai ASU, who participated in a contemporary art master class in Poland. Since 2005, modern dance has been taught by Banu Duisebayevna Turgumbayeva, a KazGozhenPI graduate and acting associate professor of the choreography department.

Master classes and festivals with various instructors of modern techniques, including improvisation and physical theater, have made an invaluable contribution to the development of modern dance in Kazakhstan.

The first contemporary dance festival, *Dance Hive*, was held at the Seleznev Kazakh Art University and organized by Zhanat Baidaralin and Bulat Dzhantayev in 1998.

Contemporary choreography is constantly evolving—teachers, choreographers, and ballet masters are continually exploring new movements, studying various choreographic styles and teaching methods. Contemporary dance techniques are rapidly gaining momentum in Kazakhstan, and this is reflected in audience recognition both domestically and internationally. Modern dance in Kazakhstan is as old as independence and a result of our country's openness policy.

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